

THE LIGHT SCATTERING BEHAVIOUR OF ALUMINIUM SUCCINATE GEL-FORMING SYSTEM

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The changes in depolarisation values and the intensity of transversely scattered light during the gelation process of aluminium succinate gel-forming mixtures have been studied. The results show that the particles increase in size during gelation and that they have spherical symmetry. The symmetry of the particles is not perceptibly disturbed in presence of acids and also by varying the concentration of gel-forming constituents. The intensity measurements reveal three distinct stages, viz., (i) a colloid is formed, (ii) hydration takes place, and (iii) the subsequent formation of a three-dimensional network. The density and anisotropy scattering have been separated from the total intensity and their changes during the process of gelation are discussed. The dissymmetry ratio $I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$ fails to indicate the probable shape of the particles.

This investigation deals with the study of the depolarisation and intensity measurements of the transversely scattered light during the process of gelation of aluminium succinate gels. The object of this study is to examine closely the changes taking place in the size, shape and the aggregation of the colloidal particles during the sol-gel transformation and possibly to obtain an insight in the structure of these gels. The present study is in continuation of our previous work reported earlier on the light scattering behaviour of several inorganic gel-forming systems (cf. Jabalpurwala and Desai, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 645; *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1958, 27, 20; 1957, 26, 31).

EXPERIMENTAL

Aluminium succinate gels were formed by metathesis of aluminium chloride and sodium succinate solutions (cf. Mushran and Bose, *Curr. Sci.*, 1957, 26, 47).

$\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck's pure analytical quality, 50 g.) was dissolved in CO_2 -free doubled distilled water. The strength of this solution in terms of aluminium oxinate was 102.34 g./litre. Sodium succinate (C.P.) was purified by recrystallisation, and a known weight of the recrystallised sample was dissolved to obtain a 3M/20 solution. These two solutions were made dust-free by filtering them several times through sintered bed funnel (A.G. 201 \times 4). A known volume of aluminium chloride solution (A) was taken in one test-tube and in another test-tube was taken the solution of sodium succinate (B), diluted with the requisite amount of distilled water so that the total volume of the gel-forming system was always 42.0 c.c. The two solutions were mixed and the resulting mixture was shaken for about 30 seconds. For the measurements of depolarisation and the intensity of scattered light, the gel-forming mixture was transferred to the optical cell and the measurements were made on the gel-forming system at certain known intervals of time. The depolarisation measurements were made by the well-known Cornu's method (cf. Prasad and Doss, *J. Coll. Sci.*, 1949, 4, 349), taking all the necessary precautions, and the intensity of the scattered light was measured by the photomultiplier method, using the photomultiplier tube. The details of the circuit arrangement were described by Sundaram and Desai (*Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci.*, 1954, 20, 598). The time of setting of gels was determined by Fleming's method (*Z. Physik*, 1902, 41, 427).

The depolarisation values ρ_μ , ρ_v , ρ_h and the values of the intensity measurements I_{90} during the process of gelation in presence of varying concentrations of the constituents of the

gel-forming mixture and of acids are recorded in Tables I and II. The depolarisation values are expressed in percentages and the values of intensity are expressed in arbitrary units.

TABLE I

A=15.0 c.c. B=22.8 c.c. Time of setting=195.0 mins. A=13.8 c.c. B=22.8 c.c. Time of setting=130.0 mins.

Time	ρ_{μ}	ρ_v	ρ_h	I_{90°	$I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$	ρ_{μ}	ρ_v	ρ_h	I_{90°	$I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$
1 min.	0.69	11.00	4.05	0.85	11.00	3.81
5	1.11	..	36.11	15.13	4.18	1.20	0.28	29.48	16.50	4.00
10	1.20	0.28	29.48	37.13	4.50	1.85	0.32	21.25	26.13	4.17
20	1.40	..	24.32	46.75	4.81	2.10	0.32	18.00	33.00	4.39
40	1.40	..	24.32	46.75	4.81	2.10	0.32	18.00	49.50	4.65
60	1.40	0.28	..	46.75	4.81	2.65	0.38	17.16	56.38	4.92
80	1.40	..	24.32	50.88	5.10	3.80	0.49	14.74	60.50	5.20
100	2.51	0.38	17.58	52.25	5.15	4.71	0.49	11.53	81.13	5.60
120	3.80	0.49	14.74	70.13	5.40	5.99	0.49	8.77	105.00	6.18
140	4.33	..	12.90	74.25	5.48	6.22	0.49	8.49	112.50	6.25
160	4.52	0.49	11.85	81.13	5.61	6.22	0.49	8.49	115.00	6.30
180	5.33	0.49	9.94	90.00	5.83	6.22	0.49	8.49	115.00	6.30
200	5.77	0.49	9.35	102.50	6.05
220	5.77	0.49	9.35	105.00	6.18
240	5.77	0.49	9.35	105.00	6.18

TABLE II

A=15.0 c.c. B=24.0 c.c. Time of setting=155.0 mins. A=15.0 c.c. B=24.0 c.c. Time of setting=160.0 mins.
 C=3.0 c.c. HCl (0.1 N) C=3.0 c.c. HNO₃ (0.1 N).

Time	ρ_{μ}	ρ_v	ρ_h	I_{90°	$I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$	ρ_{μ}	ρ_v	ρ_h	I_{90°	$I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$
1 min.	0.62	11.00	3.87	0.62	11.00	3.87
5	0.69	0.19	..	16.50	4.00	0.69	1.19	38.29	16.50	4.00
10	1.11	34.38	4.21	1.01	..	29.48	30.25	4.23
20	1.20	0.28	29.48	39.88	4.53	1.01	0.23	29.48	38.50	4.48
40	1.30	..	27.10	39.38	4.53	1.01	0.23	..	38.50	4.48
60	1.40	0.28	24.32	45.38	4.67	1.40	..	24.32	44.00	4.85
80	1.40	0.28	24.32	46.75	4.75	1.40	0.28	24.32	49.50	5.15
100	1.97	0.32	19.82	56.38	5.27	1.85	0.32	21.25	60.50	5.45
120	3.43	0.49	15.52	64.63	5.59	3.43	0.49	15.52	74.25	5.70
140	4.52	0.49	12.19	82.50	5.93	4.92	0.49	11.20	82.50	5.90
160	5.54	0.49	9.65	97.50	6.14	5.54	0.49	9.65	97.50	6.14
180	5.54	0.49	9.65	100.00	6.19	5.54	0.49	9.65	100.00	6.23
200	5.54	0.49	9.65	100.00	6.19	5.54	0.49	9.65	100.00	6.23

From the tables both the initial and final values of ρ_v appear to show very little deviation from zero and that there is no appreciable change in the ρ_v values during the setting time. It can thus be inferred that the system contains particles which are spherical in shape. Further, it is seen that the variation in the concentration of the sodium succinate as well as aluminium chloride has no appreciable effect on the ρ_v values. Similar observations have been made when acids are added to these systems. It can thus be concluded that the symmetry of the particles in the gel-forming system under investigation is not perceptibly disturbed under these conditions. On the other hand, a general decrease in the values of ρ_h with the increase of time has been observed. These results indicate that the gelation is accompanied by increase in the size of the particles due to aggregation. The final values of ρ_h , which are about 10%, indicate that the size of the particles formed is fairly big as compared with the wave-length of the incident light used. Further, it has been observed that the values of ρ_h are higher in systems containing higher concentration of aluminium chloride. These systems therefore contain particles of comparatively small size. This is due to the peptising action of Al³⁺ ions. With increase in the concentration of sodium succinate, the values of ρ_h are found to decrease. This is attributed to the coagulating effect of this electrolyte. The addition of acids, on the other hand, results in imparting higher values of ρ_h to the system, which is due to the peptisation of larger aggregates in their presence.

The changes in the value of ρ_{μ} during the presence of gelation are due to the increase in values of ρ_v and decrease in the values of ρ_b , as ρ_{μ} depends on both these quantities (cf. Krishnan, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 1A, 717, 782).

DISCUSSION

Intensity Measurements.—The changes in the intensity values of the transversely scattered light during the gelation are recorded in Tables I-II and are shown graphically in Figure 1. The intensity of the scattered light is observed to rise rapidly at first. It then remains steady for some time, and then there is again a rise in intensity, but this increase is comparatively small and more gradual than the initial rise. The intensity changes thus fall into three distinct steps, indicating that there are three distinct stages in the gel-formation. The following explanation seems plausible.

In the initial stage, the scattering centres are being formed so that their number goes on increasing with time and, hence, the rapid increase in the intensity. The gel-forming substance formed as a result of the reaction between aluminium chloride and sodium succinate may be either aluminium succinate or a basic succinate of aluminium. It is possible that aluminium hydroxide may also be present in the gel-forming system formed as a result of hydrolysis of aluminium salt. Now ordinarily, hydration or solvation should proceed along with the formation of scattering centres, but the hydroxyl group present in the gel-forming system will delay the hydration of the particles. Viscosity measurements in the initial stage showed that the hydration could not have been supposed to be functioning simultaneously with the formation of the gel-forming particles. The rapid increase in the intensity of the scattered light in the initial stage may thus be attributed to the formation of the colloidal particles in the system. At the end of the initial stage, the number of scattering centres formed reaches a maximum; thereafter, it appears that the particles undergo hydration and since water, bound or free, has the same refractive index, there is hardly any change in the intensity during this stage. The constant value of the intensity of the scattered light in the second stage may be thus attributed to the hydration of the gel-forming particles. At the end of the second stage, when the hydration is assumed to be complete, the aggregates of the colloid particles will begin to form due to which there will be a change in the size and shape of the

particles. Consequently, the intensity of the scattered light will begin to rise, and since this process is slow and gradual, the rise in the intensity will take place gradually and will not be as rapid as that in which the number of particles increases in the initial stage. The third stage of intensity changes during gelation represents this behaviour. The rise in the intensity of the scattered light during this stage is thus attributed to the formation of three-dimensional network in building of the gel structure.

Density and Anisotropy Scattering.—The density and the anisotropy scattering have been separated from the total intensity of the transversely scattered light. The total intensity, I_{90° , is made up of density scattering, I_D , and anisotropy scattering, I_A . Zimm, Stein and Doty (*Polymer Bull.*, 1945, 1, 90) have shown that the effect of anisotropy would be to increase the total intensity of scattering by a factor: $\rho = \frac{2\rho_v}{1+\rho_v}$.

Hence, the density scattering (I_D) would be given by

$$I_D = I / \left(\frac{6+6\rho}{6-7\rho} \right) \text{ i.e. } I_D = I \times \frac{6-7\rho}{6+6\rho}$$

and therefore the anisotropy scattering I_A would be given by

$$I_A = I - I_D = I \times \frac{13\rho}{6+6\rho}$$

The values of I_D and I_A , calculated by the above equations, are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Aluminium chloride = 15.0 c.c. Sodium succinate = 24.0 c.c. Time of setting = 135.0 mins.

Time	ρ_v	$\rho = \frac{2\rho_v}{1+\rho_v}$	$\frac{6-7\rho}{6+6\rho}$	I_{90°	I_D	I_A
10 mins.	0.28	0.0056	0.9977	34.38	34.30	0.08
20	0.28	0.0056	0.9977	45.38	45.28	0.10
40	0.32	0.0064	0.9862	46.75	46.12	0.63
60	0.38	0.0076	0.9833	50.50	49.12	0.84
80	0.43	0.0086	0.9815	57.75	56.69	1.06
100	0.49	0.0098	0.9790	82.50	80.69	1.81
120	0.49	0.0098	0.9790	100.00	97.90	2.10
140	0.49	0.0098	0.9790	120.00	117.50	2.50
160	0.49	0.0098	0.9790	120.00	117.50	2.50

It will be seen that the values of the density scattering, I_D , increase during the process of gel formation. Since the variation in I_D values is connected with the changes in the size of the particles, it can be inferred that the size of the particles increases gradually during the process of gelation. The values of anisotropy scattering, I_A , are found to be initially low, but as the gelation proceeds, the values of I_A show a little increase and become constant after the gel is set. The anisotropy scattering I_A would indicate the changes in the shape and/or structure of the particles. These observations would therefore show that in the initial stage, the particles appear to remain almost spherical and as the gelation proceeds, they tend to be anisotropic in shape and/or structure. The constant value of I_A after the gel is set would indicate that the anisotropic nature of the particles would not change after the process of gelation is complete.

A close examination of the changes in I_D and I_A values during the gelation would reveal that variation in the former values is more pronounced than in the latter. It can therefore be inferred

from these observations that the density scattering I_D predominates over the anisotropy scattering I_A throughout the process of gelation. This means that the increase in size of the particles is a predominant factor in the process of gelation, rather than increase in the anisotropy.

Dissymmetry: Ratio $I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$.— The values of the ratio $I_{45^\circ}/I_{135^\circ}$ are recorded in the last column of Tables I and II. Since it has been inferred from the ρ_v values that the particles have almost spherical symmetry, it is expected that the dissymmetry should attain a very high value with the ultimate enormous growth of the scattering centres. The observed values of dissymmetry show a discrepancy from the values expected. In a gel-forming system, a three-dimensional net-work is formed and, as a consequence, the individual particle loses its independence. Consequently, there is a possibility of considerable multiple scattering and absorption which will affect the value of dissymmetry. The observed discrepancy in the value of this ratio appears to be due to multiple scattering and absorption in this system.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. M. B. Kabadi, M.Sc., Ph.D., for helpful suggestions and keen interest in this investigation.

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Received December 1, 1959.